

EMERGENCE OF CREATIVE EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN.

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Annotation: *Creativity is a phenomenon that contributes to the creation of something new and useful in a new and useful sense. In other words, creativity is the most necessary tool for creating a new abstract thing (work, music, idea or start-up) or a physical discovery.*

Keywords: *creative, technology, information-methodical, educational, process, interactive, skill, person, educator.*

Introduction

One of the efforts of the Republic of Uzbekistan to reform the education system is to ensure that teachers work in line with modern requirements, have a deep knowledge, skills, abilities and culture for the development of comprehensively developed individuals. .

This in itself introduced the concept of "creativity" to the science of music, which studies the laws of musical creation. In particular, the current development of scientific knowledge, the impact of creativity on the development of the individual, society and the state requires an in-depth study of this issue from a scientific and pedagogical point of view.

The creative development of the Uzbek education system with new approaches The problems of system formation are rooted in spiritual and moral values.

The current state of education and upbringing is characterized by the stability of music in higher education.

Discussion

Creativity is a multifaceted concept. Creativity, the ability to create new things based on existing knowledge, and the diversity of ideas are the basis of creativity, allowing human abilities to go beyond. The development of this definition is gradual.

Today, a music teacher needs a wide range of knowledge, in-depth knowledge of creative psychology, and interactive games. International experts have described creative thinking as "giving new ideas and solutions." It has six aspects:

1) Describe, feel, observe, empathize with relevant experiential information;

2) Research, search and develop ideas;

3) Building relationships, applying perspectives to industries;

4) Playing with unusual or bold ideas;

5) Imagination, expression development, discovery of a new product;

6) Recognition of the novelty of the solution;¹

The task of creativity-based education is to develop the skills that a student will need today and in the future to succeed in society. Creative thinking is an important skill that today's youth should have.²

Results

The development of creativity in students depends on the level of knowledge of students in mastering the content of education, the level of mastery, the source of education, didactic tasks, requires the organization of the teaching process accordingly.

In this case, the following pedagogical conditions must be observed:

- Provide an environment in which learners are encouraged to engage in creative activities, develop cognitive needs, and demonstrate independence in the learning process;

- To create a favorable environment for students to think creatively, to tolerate the various ideas and ideas expressed by students, and to ensure their active participation in the learning process, to ensure that each student deciding on the growth of their ability to think creatively, regularly stimulating their creative activity;

Individualization of the learning process based on the characteristics, needs and intellectual potential of the learner;

- To develop students' skills of working individually, in small groups and in teams, to expand their creative potential, to encourage them to accept non-standard solutions, along with standard solutions, ready to solve their problems;

- Selection and implementation of interactive forms and methods of interactive learning, which allow to develop and improve the cognitive

¹ "Scope of assessment of creative thinking in PISA research" under the general editorship of U.Sharifkhodjayev and D.Norbayeva. Tashkent - 2020. Page 6

² Lucas, B. And E.Spencer (2017), Teaching Creative Thinking: Developing Learners Who Generate Ideas and Can Think Critically, Cown House Publishing, https://bookshop.canterbury.ac.uk/Teaching-Creative-Thinking-Developing-learnes-Who-generate-ideas-and-can-think-critically_9781785832369 (accessed on 26 March 2018)

knowledge in practice, which is the basis for the development of creative activity, etc .;

An important condition for the development of creative abilities of students in Uzbekistan is the creation of a free-creative environment in the educational process, the teaching process based on the interaction and interaction of professors, teachers and students. consists of putting.

There are a number of scholars who develop students' creative abilities:

- Development of creative thinking skills, the formation of creative activity, strengthening the research process and problem-based research;
- Creating conditions for students to solve problems creatively and develop creative activities;
- Achieving approaches to the creative experience of students as an integral part of the content of professional needs and future professional activity;
- Creating a favorable creative and collaborative environment for students to demonstrate their creative abilities ...

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the development of learners is one of the most important tasks today, and based on the above theoretical foundations, we can conclude that:

- Interactive teaching methods and technologies play an important role in the formation of creative abilities in learners. The development of creativity has a specific content, tools, pedagogical features and methods of the teaching process.
- Systematic study of pedagogical needs, interests, areas of special importance of students, it is necessary to identify effective ways to overcome the psychological barriers encountered in the organization of creative activity of the student.

To abandon the pre-planning of future lessons, to form and develop critical, creative thinking in future teachers, to force them to think creatively, to invent new ideas, to change the attitude to education, will be a key factor in motivating them to succeed. It is not about whether the learner is creative or not, but about organizing lessons in the spirit of creativity, trying to try new ideas in the learning process.

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